

The Future of Mankind—God’s Momentous Speech

With Four Pauses

Revelation 21:5, 6

Part of a longer analysis into the pauses in speech in the Bible

See *A Study in Silence*

The purpose of this paper was to examine the purpose of the three pauses in God’s momentous speech in Revelation 21:3–5. The first pause allowed for an immense line to be drawn after he said, “The former things have passed away”. The second pause framed the great promise: “Look! I am making all things new”. The third pause gave John time to write this down. The fourth pause came before the single word Γέγοναν meaning “done!”.

Revelation 21:5, 6

καὶ εἶπεν ὁ καθήμενος ἐπὶ τῷ θρόνῳ Ἰδοὺ καινὰ ποιῶ πάντα καὶ λέγει Γράψον ὅτι οὗτοι οἱ λόγοι πιστοὶ καὶ ἀληθινοὶ εἰσιν

καὶ εἶπέν μοι Γέγοναν ἐγὼ τὸ Ἄλφα καὶ τὸ Ὠ ἡ ἀρχὴ καὶ τὸ τέλος ἐγὼ τῷ διψῶντι δώσω ἐκ τῆς πηγῆς τοῦ ὕδατος τῆς ζωῆς δωρεάν

The vision that John saw in chapter 21 reveals the moment when God will take back control of the Earth. The outcomes for mankind are described in four speeches by God. Speech one (verses 3 and 4); speech two and three (verse 5); speech four (verses 6 to 8). In between are three pauses.

Speech one is introduced by John with these words: “I heard a loud voice from the throne say”. This is the speech, which seems to conform to Hebrew poetic parallelism:

- A Ἴδοὺ ἡ σκηνὴ τοῦ θεοῦ μετὰ τῶν ἀνθρώπων
- B καὶ σκηνώσει μετ' αὐτῶν
- C καὶ αὐτοὶ λαοὶ αὐτοῦ ἔσονται
- D καὶ αὐτὸς ὁ θεὸς μετ' αὐτῶν ἔσται
- E καὶ ἐξαλείψει πᾶν δάκρυον ἐκ τῶν ὀφθαλμῶν αὐτῶν
- F καὶ ὁ θάνατος οὐκ ἔσται ἔτι
- G οὔτε πένθος οὔτε κραυγὴ οὔτε πόνος οὐκ ἔσται ἔτι
- H τὰ πρῶτα ἀπῆλθαν

- A *Look! The tent of God is with mankind,*
- B *and he will reside with them,*
- C *and they will be his peoples.*
- D *And God himself will be with them.*
- E *And he will wipe out every tear from their eyes,*
- F *and death will be no more,*
- G *neither will mourning nor outcry nor pain be anymore.*
- H *The former things have passed away.*

When in verse 3, μετὰ is used with the genitive—μετὰ τῶν—it shows relationship, association, or companionship—physically, socially or spiritually (Matthew 9:11; 16:27; 20:20; 22:16). Four times God declares that he will be in such a companionship with mankind with a rising sense of closeness.

The use of σκηνὴ and σκηνώσει suggest God's presence amongst his people Israel in the wilderness. But it is one thing that his tent is with his peoples; it is another that he is dwelling with them in their camp. And if that term could be construed as somewhat temporary, he goes on to assert even closer fellowship in the concluding couplet. There is a matching order and words in C/D: καὶ αὐτοὶ λαοὶ/καὶ αὐτὸς ὁ θεός—'and they peoples of him will be/and he the God of them will be'. According to Metzger λαοὶ is better supported than λαός. And "peoples" is a better match to ἀνθρώπων, "mankind" in A. Peoples and God in perfect union and harmony.

The result is that all the effects of the rebellion God will remove. It is therefore somewhat surprising that F is not before E—that the penalty for the rebellion, death is not the first effect to be removed since death was the first penalty (Genesis 2:17; 3:3). But that is to take this order technically rather than emotionally. So it

is the emotional impact of death that is first addressed: *καὶ ἐξαλείψει πᾶν δάκρυον ἐκ τῶν ὀφθαλμῶν αὐτῶν*. It takes great trust to allow someone to put their finger into your eye—even if it is to wipe a tear away. We know when we really trust someone: we completely relax. The single δάκρυον “tear” coupled with πᾶν “all” and matched with the plural ὀφθαλμῶν “eyes”, tells us that every single tear has been noticed and every single tear will be wiped away from all eyes.

E, F, G, H might be chiasmic. If that was the case then “the former things” relate to the tears; ‘wiping out’ pairs with “passed away”; the centre then would all apply to death and its effects. Maybe that is too narrow. Without doubt the brief statement τὰ πρῶτα ἀπῆλθαν, “The former things have passed away”, with ἀπῆλθαν as an aorist, draws a immense line.

Having drawn that line God made his first pause. This and the subsequent pause surround Ἴδου καινὰ ποιῶ πάντα, “Look! I am making all things new”, framing it, giving the promise of renewal all the weight of its significance.

Ἴδου is being used in the sense of the Hebrew demonstrative particle הִנֵּה. It is usually rendered “Look!” although seeing is not necessarily the meaning of the term. God is the first one to use הִנֵּה. He does so after blessing Adam and Eve: “Look!”, he says with all the joy that comes from being generous, “I have given to you all vegetation bearing seed which is on the surface of the whole earth and every tree on which there is the fruit of a tree bearing seed. To you let it serve as food” (Genesis 1:29). The next occasion is at the completion of the sixth day, “After that God saw everything he had made and, look! [it was] very good” (Genesis 1:31). The third time it is used, there is great sadness: “God saw the earth and, look! it was ruined, because all flesh had ruined its way on the earth” (Genesis 6:12). That is quite some pair of verses—1:31 and 6:12. So how appropriate that at the moment God promised to renew all things—back to his original intention—that he should preface it with הִנֵּה. We should share in this excitement.

The present tense of ποιῶ which is part of a series of presents in verses 3 and 4 is a statement of God’s certainty that this *will* occur. Indeed, after a third pause at the end of verse 5, God confirms this: “They have come to pass! I am the Alpha and the Omega, the beginning and the end” (verse 6). The present tense could also imply that there will be a process of making all things new.

After this extensive guarantee another silence. Time for John to think about these momentous words. This is mankind’s future.

Then comes a divine command: Γράψον, aorist imperative, “Write!”, do not let these words pass without being recorded, preserved so that they can be passed on to others. This is the good news of the Kingdom, when God’s will is done as in Heaven also upon Earth (Matthew 6:10), and it is this good news of the Kingdom that Jesus said would be shared with all as a witness (Matthew 24:14).

Further reason for recording these words follows: ὅτι οὗτοι οἱ λόγοι πιστοὶ καὶ ἀληθινοὶ εἰσιν. In case anyone should think that God’s promise is too good to be true, he uses two adjectives to compound its credibility. The first is πιστός, meaning trustworthy, faithful, reliable, believable, loyal (Turner). This word is used to describe God (πιστὸς ὁ θεός, 1 Corinthians 1:9) and those who represent him (πιστὸς δοῦλος, Matthew 24:45).

The other is ἀληθινός which means genuine, bone fide, authentic, not counterfeit, whether something is truly what it claims to be, as opposed to a lesser imitation. Jesus himself is described by both: πιστὸς...καὶ ἀληθινός (Revelation 19:11).

Then comes the third pause. A pause for emphasis and a pause for John to obey the command to write these monumental words down.

The first word after the pause is Γέγοναν. One word forms a sentence. This is the perfect indicative, third person plural of γίνομαι. The object is the words, hence third person. “They are done” in English, or closer to the succinctness, “done”. This one word Γέγοναν marks the moment where the story of creation, fall, redemption and new creation reaches its irreversible fulfilment. This is breathtaking economy. One word carries the weight of history’s fulfilment. That was worthy of a pause before it was uttered.

Immediately after Γέγοναν, God declared: ἐγὼ τὸ Ἄλφα καὶ τὸ Ὠ ἢ ἀρχὴ καὶ τὸ τέλος, “I am the Alpha and the Omega, the beginning and the end”.

It is as though Jehovah himself were signing for faithful mankind a guarantee, or title deed, to these future blessings.... So certain are these promises of Jehovah that he speaks as though they were already fulfilled: “They have come to pass!” Is not Jehovah “the Alpha and the Omega . . . , the One who is and who was and who is coming, the Almighty”? (Revelation 1:8) Indeed he is! He himself declares: “I am the first and I am the last, and*

* See Appendix, page 5.

besides me there is no God.” (Isaiah 44:6) As such, he can inspire prophecies and fulfill them in every detail (Re, page 304).

Looking back at the four speeches and three pauses, we note that the speeches are introduced with a variety of forms of λέγω. Speech one (verse 3): the great voice from the throne λεγούσης, the present participle. Speech two (verse 5): εἶπεν, the aorist indicative. Speech three (verse 5): λέγει, the present indicative. Speech four (verse 6): εἶπέν, the aorist indicative. This switching between present and aorist is intriguing. The present draws the reader into the immediacy of the moment. The aorist is completed “action as punctiliar, or momentary” (*Int*, page 1171). The indicative was used when a speaker wanted to express something that was for them a fact, an assertion or reality.

Let’s analyse the use of the two presents first. The events that run up to the divine proclamation in verse 3 concern the arrival of the complete bride of Christ. According to Jesus, this marriage forms the Kingdom of the Heavens (Matthew 22:1–14). And “just as earthly Jerusalem became the seat of government in ancient Israel, the magnificent New Jerusalem and her Bridegroom make up the government” that will rule over the Earth (*Re* page 302, Psalm 2; Daniel 2:44; 7:13, 14). It would seem appropriate that God would want to draw John into the immediacy of this exciting moment since the results of God’s Kingdom will solve all of mankind’s problems. When a narrative switches from the past tense, like εἶπεν—“he said”, to the present like λέγει, it invites the reader to step inside the moment, as though the event was unfolding right now. So in verse 5, when John writes λέγει, “he says” or “he is saying” (*Int*), we are right there with John as he hears the command: Γράψον, “Write”. The audience is not merely being told what happened, but they are being placed in the scene—watching, hearing it happen live; we become eyewitnesses with John, we are moved to imagine his response as he hastily pens the words which will form this record.

The two aorist indicatives comprise the introductions to the two momentous statements: Ἴδου καινὰ ποιῶ πάντα, “Look! I am making all things new” and Γέγοναν, “They have come to pass”. The aorist indicatives make the following statements historic and emphatic.

APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate those names which have the first two syllables of the divine name as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a y in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a w. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֱלֹהֵינוּ does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and יו, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Int* *The Kingdom Interlinear of the Greek Scriptures*, Watchtower Bible and Tract Society of New York, International Bible Students Association Brooklyn, New York, 1985.
- Metzger Bruce M. Metzger, *A Textual Commentary on the Greek New Testament*, Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 1994.
- Re.* *Revelation—Its Grand Climax at Hand!*, Watchtower Bible and Tract Society of New York, Inc. Brooklyn, 1988.
- Turner Nigel Turner, *Christian Words*, T&T Clark, 1980.

Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984, unless otherwise indicated.

The Introduction to this edition of NW contains this explanation:

Where “you” is printed in small capital letters, it shows that the pronoun is plural. Also, where the plural number of a verb is not apparent, its plurality is indicated by printing it in small capital letters. If the context already clearly indicates plurality, then no special capitalization is used.